

KEY INDICATORS

With 90,938 hectares, the Netherlands had 5% of its farmland under organic management in 2024, considerably less than the EU (11.1%). Growth from 2001-2024 was modest compared to most other countries; the organic farmland area only doubled. In the Netherlands, organic retail sales amounted to 1,880 million euros or 3.7% of all retail sales, similar to the EU organic share of food retail sales.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

35,877 ha (1.8%)

90,938 ha (5%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

153.5%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

16,001 ha (2.6%)

34,233 ha (3.4%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

598 ha (2.9%)

962 ha (2.6%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

18,890 ha (1.9%)

55,743 ha (7.2)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

15,277 t (38.7%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

1,528 (1.5%)

2,099 (4%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

35

Processors

N/D

1,146

Importers

N/D

505

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

343 M €

1,880 M€ (3.7%)

Per Capita Consumption

21.5 €

105 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

N/D

Imports

N/D

933,370 t

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN NETHERLANDS

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN THE NETHERLANDS

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Bionext and LEI

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

After a long period when the Netherlands was the only country in Europe not to support conversion to or maintenance of organic farming, the introduction of support for organic farming at the top level of the national eco-scheme marks a significant change in approach. The Netherlands CAP Strategic Plan sets a target of 6.5% of UAA to be supported as organic by 2027/8, with just over 6% of total environmental support and less than 2% of CAP funds allocated to organic. Some provinces, e.g. Overijssel, provide additional conversion support not detailed here.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

2018

2027

Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	0 kha	109 kha
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	0%	6.5%
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	0%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	0 M€	16 M€
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	0 €	200 €

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P1)*	95 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	964 M€	6.2%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	576 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	4,899 M€	1.9%

Organic eco-scheme expenditure estimated from per hectare rates and R29 indicators

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	N/D	0	0	0	0
	2023	P1	200	200	200	200
Change from 2019 to 2023			∞	∞	∞	∞
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	N/D	0	0	0	0
	2023	P1	200	200	200	200
Change from 2019 to 2023			∞	∞	∞	∞
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Although the Netherlands had three action plans from 2001, there was a long period since 2010 with no new action plans. The latest action plan for 2023-2030 sets an ambitious target of 15% of UAA to be organic by 2030, making the target challenging, also given the CAP CSP target of 6.5% UAA supported as organic in 2027/8.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	None	None	None
Current Action Plan	2023-30	15% of UAA by 2030	25% of public procurement

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (N/D)

PRODUCTION

Support via eco-scheme introduced, with additional conversion support through regional rural area transition funds, and investments via sustainable agriculture investment fund

MARKETS

Sector-led supply chain developments; 25% target for central government procurement – other authorities to follow; explore options for hospitality catering; ambitious retailer goals for potatoes, fruit and vegetables; national-funded market development scheme; support export development; encourage retailer certification to reduce packaging; review control system to reduce costs; revise land leasing regulations; establishment of bio-districts

INFORMATION

Increase awareness of organic products and EU logo; review presentation with retailers; communicate sustainability benefits; establish national conversion helpline; encourage knowledge exchange with other sectors; develop use of farm advisory service for conversion advice and business planning; identify opportunities to improve knowledge dissemination including training, education also of advisors; develop research and innovation agenda aligned with EU programmes; research on how food services can contribute to increased sales

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in the Netherlands is 20%. The Netherlands was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Aquaculture was not highlighted in the current national organic action plan from 2023. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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